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Digital Identity Construction & Self-Presentation in the Network Society

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Abstract

Nowadays, people's lives are becoming digitalized day by day, and the understanding of social reality includes the modern virtual world. Technological changes and developments and digital network platforms, which have become more and more widely used day by day, increase the virtual reality of people, damage their ties with the real life and alienate the individually. Allowing people to communicate faster and more effectively with their surroundings in society, digital network platforms have started to change and transform the way of social life. For the reproduction and perpetuation of this change and transformation, the individual constructs his/her identity according to specific elements.

Limitations

The limitations of the research are limited to the extent of the subject in the world literature and data. Research is restricted to closely related researchers and literature. It is also limited to literature survey.

Notices

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Ethical Declaration

Publishing ethics of the relevant regulations of our university; It is a national-based scientific study that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are made in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, respect for the findings and creations of others, and aims to realize these principles in the field of related disciplines.

Description

People's lives are becoming more and more digitalized every day, social understanding of reality includes the virtual world. With the technological changes and developments, the digital network platforms, which are becoming more and more widely used day by day, increase the virtual reality of people, damage their ties with real life and foreignize the individually. Allowing people to communicate faster and more effectively with their surroundings in society, digital network platforms have started to change and transform the way of social life. For this transformation and change to be reproduced and sustained, the individual constructs his/her identity according to certain factors. The digital interactivity, which is the basic relationship form of social life, transforms today's life into a digital age and society into a digital network society. Besides the realization of interaction between people, digital network platforms also create an environment for constructing virtual identity & the presentation of self.

Keywords: *Network Society, Identity, Digital Identity, Digital Identity, Digital Identity Construction, Self-Presentation.*

Abstract

Today, social life is becoming digital every day, and the understanding of social reality includes the virtual world. Changes and developments in the field of technology, digital network platforms, which are becoming more and more common day by day, increase people's virtual reality, damage their ties with real life and alienate the individual. Digital network platforms, which allow people to communicate more quickly and effectively with their environment in society, have also begun to change and transform the social life style. In order for this change and transformation to be reproduced and become permanent, the individual builds his identity according to some factors. Digital interaction, which is the basic relationship form of social life, transforms today's life into a digital age and society into a digital network society. In addition to realizing interaction between people, digital network platforms also create an environment for virtual identity construction and self-presentation.

Keywords: *Network Society, Identity, Digital Identity, Digital Identity Construction, Self-Presentation.*

Introduction

Developments, changes and transformations that have occurred in the post-modern era we are living in demonstrate that a new historical period is being experienced in social structure and relations. Changes and developments in information, internet and communication technologies in this period, as well as this new social period that humanity is still experiencing and the social structure formed are defined as the "network society".

Network Society, which means a life in which social life relations are maintained through digital technologies and a dizzyingly fast social life compared to previous social periods, is essentially a society in which internet networks are indispensable in all areas of life such as at

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work, at home, on the street, on travel, on vacation, etc., and information technologies have taken a big place in the daily lives of everyone from seven to seventy. The identity, which is significantly influenced and shaped by social developments and the characteristics of the network society, is beginning to be re-formed in a wider social environment under the influence of different factors and depending on different values and global cultural dynamics. The experiences continuing on the network also transform identities into digital personalities (Altun, 2017).

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With the advancement and development of technology, the global spread of the internet has influenced human life in many aspects and has led to the change and transformation of new communication environments. These changes and transformations, supported by digital networks and web 2.0, have brought along social network-based communication and, accordingly, virtual identities. These virtual relationships, which have developed as a new form of communication in the digital society, have also brought a new dimension to self-presentation. The ways in which individuals express themselves, share their information, and socialize with the public have changed and transformed with digitalization, increasing its impact on meaning and importance in society. As such, people's sharing about their own lives on digital networks, identity constructions and self-presentations have started to be reshaped in the context of the social environment they have interacted in (Demirel, 2021).

Methodology

Through this conceptual study, it has been tried to understand how virtual identity construction and self-presentation take place on digital platforms with the technological developments in the network society and what are the effects of this on the effects on the person. Network society, identity, digital identity, digital identity construction and digital self-presentation were defined and their dynamics were tried to be revealed. The effects of these dynamics on digital identity construction and self-presentation were analyzed, and false identities and self-presentations created and displayed in digital network environments were examined. Within this concept, the theoretical framework on network society, identity, digital identity, digital identity construction and self-presentation was presented by reviewing the relevant literature, and then the effects of virtual identity construction and self-presentation on the individual were demonstrated.

Literature Review

Considering the development of humanity, it is observed that technological developments, especially the developments in communication technologies, are one of the most important factors affecting the change and transformations in social life. Technological developments, changes and transformations shape the social structure, social culture and institutions, and continue to direct the life and development of humanity today, as in the past (Yenilmez Kaçar, 2020).

Revolutionizing the communication methods of societies, the internet, computer and mobile technologies, which have left their mark on recent times, have accelerated the lives of individuals and the routine flow of life by affecting every aspect of daily societal life. Thus, the world has become smaller and almost a "global village" as a result of the ability to provide information to more than one person at the same time and quickly, and to overcome distances by enabling individuals to be aware of each other within seconds. In this new network society, where the Internet is the most important factor, information in social, economic, cultural and political fields is transmitted through the networks of massive communications tools (Yenilmez Kaçar, 2020). The developments in the field of technology as well as the significant social changes in social life and the interaction of individuals through a global network without time and space limitations have led the society of this age to be defined as a "network society". In this society, relationships and interaction in social life are carried out through a network and a social structure that is necessarily connected to the network has emerged, from individuals to the largest corporate organizations. In the analysis of future research in this field, it is understood that network-based social structures will continue to increase day by day (Altun, 2017).

According to the Current Turkish Dictionary, definition of the concept of identity is as the following: "*The whole of the qualities and characteristics that show what kind of person a person is as a social being; the document that identifies who a person is, identity document, identity card, identification card, hüviyet; the whole of the features that help to identify any object*" (<https://www.tdk.gov.tr/>).

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With a multidimensional content as the equivalent of people's cultural values, social status and roles, identity is a concept related to the science of psychology that expresses people's attitudes, behaviors, emotions, thoughts and mental states. The individualistic aspect of the concept of identity depends on the individual's answers to the "Who am I?" question. Moreover, the social dimension occurs as a result of the extent to which the individual is integrated with the values of the social group to which he or she feels he or she belongs. Throughout their lives, people are concerned with how and in what way they are perceived by others in their social environment. In this context, people's perceptions of themselves give clues about how other people treat them and how they evaluate themselves. People often shape their attitudes and behaviors to have a positive impact on other people (Yıldız, 2021).

Identity is constructed through a process of interaction and over a period of time. In this construction process, network society and mass media have a significant impact. In the process of identity construction, these social network platforms cause individuals to fall into the misconception that there is an environment where they can express themselves freely, thus strengthening the common understanding of identity. These platforms, which make individuals fall into the misconception of freedom, are social media networks that have emerged and developed with the rapidly spreading internet in social life. Forms of identity, which were formed by local dynamics in accordance with the social life environment and culture in which people lived in the past, have undergone a great change and transformation with social media platforms in the network society, and new types of identity have emerged (Yıldız, 2021). Individuals communicate with other individuals who have become their audience through these network environments with their current and ideal identities or reconstructed identities. By means of online identities on social network platforms, individuals find opportunities for interaction that they cannot physically do face-to-face, they are able to learn the thoughts and opinions of other users by communicating and interacting with them, they can exhibit their existing identities or they can instantly construct new identities for themselves. Thus, it causes individuals' possible identities in social networks to become their real identities and shows the beginning of the change in the perception of identity and transformation. (Yıldız, 2021).

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To consider identity as a given is to assume that it depends on unchanging and fixed factors. Identity, including its elements and/or its meaning as a whole, changes and transforms over time. This means that identity is constructed in process. This quality is related to new experiences and life activities in a process of constant renewal. Identities are always in a process of construction, as even the newest quickly becomes obsolete. For the construction of identities, we draw inspiration from history, geography, biology, productive and reproductive social institutions, social memory, individual thoughts, power apparatuses and religious texts. Individuals, social groups and societies, however, process all these data according to the social structure, social conditions and cultural norms in which they live and reorganize the meaning of all these values (Altun, 2017).

Another of the opportunities provided by digital network environments is that they reveal structures that offer individuals new possibilities in self-disclosure and self-presentation. Self-disclosure and self-presentation are seen as two important factors for creating a holistic identity. In this way, individuals can have more self-knowledge as a result of the social roles they present to others and their interactions with others. On online digital network platforms, individuals can change or reconstruct their identities more easily. In addition, they can also change and transform the environments they are in and thus have the opportunity to construct a more holistic identity (Boz, 2012).

Digital identities, which help individuals introduce themselves to other individuals on social network platforms, are defined as virtual attitudes and behaviors blended with technological possibilities. Digital identity users who organize their attitudes and behaviors in social networks according to moral rules can make accurate analyses about how to interpret their behaviors in terms of cultural and social values. When interacting in online network environments, such individuals become people who act in accordance with cultural and social values and exhibit attitudes and behaviors within a moral framework. Digital identities, which can be changed and reorganized, when necessary, enable individuals to be sure of who they interact with in digital environments. It is expected that individuals with digital identities in virtual network environments make correct analyses and comments about the ethical implications of their attitudes and behaviors while communicating, draw a profile that is not bad according to the norms of the network society and cooperate with other people (Yıldız, 2021).

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Individuals try to comment on the reactions of other users through photos, videos and texts that they prefer to share, like and interact with on social networks, and in this framework, they structure their own content and information and construct their digital identities accordingly. In virtual network environments used by people for identity construction, identity and self-presentation, image creation, role-playing and leisure time evaluation purposes, individuals create a fluid identity by presenting information and various images of themselves without claiming reality. In social life, individuals think that their existence will gain meaning and they will be able to prove their identities as long as they are visible on these platforms with the influence of online network environments. People who build their identity construction on being visible and proving themselves on these online virtual platforms objectify other users and glorify themselves in this process (Yıldız, 2021).

One of the phenomena that have a high level of influence on the process of identity construction is the desire to be liked, the need to be accepted and loved by others in society. In this regard, social network environments provide great support and opportunities to individuals. While sharing their own content on social network platforms, individuals act with the desire to be liked by their followers and other people in the virtual network environment, and individuals can build different identities for different situations within the variable and dynamic structure of social network environments. (Yıldız, 2021).

Today, popular culture and digital network environments create faces without people. Although the magic of virtual reality, fake individuals and fake beings on network platforms attracts and attracts people, carrying the heavy burden of the identities formed by this kind of sociability on people and having to live with a 'mask' constantly creates unhappy and aimless people in society. These virtual/fake identities, which usually consist of a falsehood, a lie and a mask that the individual creates about himself/herself, make the person a 'perfect' person in his/her own life. These virtual identities, which are often created on digital networks by lying to the individual himself/herself, reduce the potential in people and clearly transform individuals into simple functional beings (Kalaman, 2016).

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These fake or anonymous identities built in digital network environments, which often contain unrealistic elements, can create a psychological burden on people. When these virtual identities that people build for themselves on social networks do not match their real identities in their offline lives, individuals are in a dilemma and this situation can cause problems in terms of mental health (Yıldız, 2021).

The suppression or forced limitation of some individual qualities and freedoms of people leads to the emergence of feelings of shame, incompleteness and falsification. Therefore, the missing sense of authenticity in the individual is tried to be eliminated through virtual/fake/false identities. In this context, the individual who wants to have what he/she is restricted or wants to access but cannot reach, wants to reach this authenticity and expectations by creating virtual/fake/fake identities on digital networks instead of revealing his/her own potential. However, these virtual identities cause individuals to create an even more ordinary personality, as opposed to achieving the originality they aim for (Kalamán, 2016). Every person tries to recognize and define himself/herself with the different answers he/she gives in response to the question "Who am I really?". The answers to questions such as who he/she is, what his/her purpose in the world is, the feelings and thoughts of other individuals about him/her, and what he/she serves throughout his/her life reveal the qualities of the self, which is the inner essence of that person. The state of being aware of oneself in an inner sense and being aware of one's existence is defined as the self. When the individual is alone with himself/herself, he/she distinguishes himself/herself from other individuals by making comments and inferences about himself/herself. The self, which is primarily an expression of one's inner journey, is the individual's realization of his/her own qualities, making intellectual comments about himself/herself and defining himself/herself as "I am this person". Self-identity, which refers to the fact that people are aware of "who" they are and that the self remains the same even if the social environment in which people live differs, generally consists of the individual's own interpretations and inferences, society's thoughts about the individual, the hopes, goals and expectations that the individual wants to achieve during his/her life (Albayrak, 2019).

Findings

Self-identity develops and changes as a result of the interaction with the social environment in which people live. The presentation of self, which refers to the efforts of individuals to keep

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control of the qualities related to themselves while introducing themselves to the society, is also one of the ways that individuals use to manage their selves. In the literature on this subject, this concept, which is also called "impression management" in the studies on this subject, states that selves should be controlled in order to have the desired effect on others (Albayrak, 2019).

The need for human beings to communicate with other individuals in society arises as a result of their being a social creature. While individuals socialize in their social lives, while meeting new people, they provide information about themselves in order to introduce themselves in friends, family and work environments. They make some efforts to leave the desired effect on the people they interact with at that moment. Instead of directly conveying the self-features he presents to others in the society without filtering them, he organizes them in line with his wishes. The individual's goal here is to control the society's thoughts about his/her own self by acquiring a self-organized according to certain qualities (Albayrak, 2019).

Individuals organize their selves according to the interpretations and value judgments of the society or the person with whom they communicate. They present their selves by adopting values they do not really believe in, lying to themselves and their environment about themselves, or behaving as if they are someone different from who they really are. The selves presented as planned ensure that social relations and interaction develop and progress in the desired direction (Albayrak, 2019).

In order to be accepted and loved by the social environment in which the individual lives, self-presentations are tried to be taken under control according to the norms and cultural expectations required by the current age. While planning the self, the products offered by popular culture, consumer culture, fashion, etc. concepts have significant effects. In today's social life, the desire to be liked physically and to strive to be flawless, to belong to a certain social status and caste by using fashionable products is one of the phenomena that serve to make people's appearance have the desired effect (Albayrak, 2019).

In most of the cases, self-presentations are realized with different looks and masks, while in some cases they are realized without masks. When the individual acts according to the person in front of him/her and behaves in the way he/she desires, it is a reason to be loved by other individuals. In the cases where this path is not chosen, the self is reflected as it really is, but still not fully under the influence of the other individuals encountered. In cases where there are facts that are hidden from others in the society, self-presentation is done without losing control.

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The fact that both self-presentation choices are controlled indicates that self-presentation is largely shaped by knowledge control. (Albayrak, 2019).

Discussion

Since the early ages, every society has been experiencing change, development and transformation. Modern social life, which is defined as a digital or digital society, is a form of society that transcends cities, national borders and continents. The themes of the enormous development of digital technologies and the cyber networks are included in the definitions of digital sociology and sociologists. Therefore, there is a period of significant increase in sociological studies and conceptualizations of the digital world and network societies (Gözüaçık, 2019).

What people think about their own personality is the way they perceive themselves. An individual's self is the most important determining quality here. The self, which is shaped within the framework of the individual's own ideas and often the comments and evaluations prepared by his/her environment, is formed by the individual's position in social life, the knowledge he/she has acquired and his/her social interactions. (Okcebe, 2019).

Online digital networks are considered as a new form of platform for self-presentation. At the same time, thanks to these environments, a new field has been opened for the research of people's identities. These interaction processes in social life are defined by Goffman as "presentation of self". In this process, individuals who make comparisons when they interact with other people make observations about the physical characteristics, ideas and behaviors of other people in society in order to make comments and inferences about themselves. Individuals who do not have a certain interpretation and judgment about their self-features, since they cannot reach a conclusion themselves, take some of the characteristics of other people as a basis and structure themselves in this direction and in a similar way (Okcebe, 2019).

Goffman states that creating social acclaim and gaining social approval constitute the fundamental building blocks of human development processes and continuity. The size of the difference between one's real image (what one thinks one is) and one's ideal image plays a major role in self-presentation. Since the increasing depth of the difference will be a factor that damages the ego of the individual, individuals try to repair their egos and maintain their internal

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consistency. However, if they can display their ideal image through digital networks, they can both reflect the image they have determined in their minds and have a closer relationship with the social environment of their dreams (Okcebe, 2019).

Self-presentation is conceptualized as the ability of individuals to shape the impressions they form about themselves while interacting with others, through the communicative means they use intentionally or unintentionally, and the ability to create a desired and admired image about themselves in the other individual. In this way, individuals can decide how they want to exist in social life, what kind of image they can acquire, and what kind of way and method they will follow in creating this image by finding and developing many options and many different ways of communication. With these ways and methods, they can access communication in digital networks much more easily than in physical life. This is one of the main reasons for choosing digital networks (Okcebe, 2019).

A generation is growing up that cannot express itself properly in their social lives but "shows" itself through digital network environments. A generation that is physically passive but mentally active, consumes fast-food, ready-made, frozen foods and all kinds of fizzy drinks, wears brands, uses expensive smart phones, consumes everything they own with a "disposable" approach, follows fashion even in middle and high school, and has the principle of "image is everything". How they live their lives, what their thoughts are, their outlook on life, etc. are not important; what is important is "how they look". In every activity and in everything, "pleasure and speed" are accepted as the basis and in parallel with this, attitudes and behaviors are exhibited with the idea of "live in the moment" with a consumption culture. In the ostentatious consumer society that brings their bodies to the forefront, individuals try to show everything they have with the understanding of "everything that is visible is good" and try to realize themselves by making themselves visible in this way. In virtual network environments, individuals instantly share and like everything they go, wear, buy, eat, drink and consume in a race. Social and cultural values are also formed around these; individuals construct package virtual identities based on form-oriented, self-centered, image and show, and present their virtual selves accordingly.

Conclusion

Network society refers to the social life style in which information, technology and the Internet have a significant global and local impact on societies, shaping the communication styles of individuals and societies, changing and transforming social structures, and creating new values and a new culture through their mutual interactions. In this context, the network society expresses radical changes and transformations from the changing and transforming family structure to individual and social relations, from working life to new identity constructions and self-presentations. One of the most important reflections of these developments is that they spread changes and transformations in individual, mass, local and global terms, making them the new way of life. (Altun, 2017).

Social network environments used in the digital society, which is the new way of life, weaken individuals' ties with the real world and increase their virtual reality. These digital network platforms, which change and develop rapidly and effectively, cause individuals to construct a virtual identity and self that is different from their real identities and selves, and to reproduce this virtual identity and self. Therefore, these digital network environments force individuals to distance themselves from their real identities and selves. As a result, there is a weakening in the ties of individuals with their social environment, causing them to become more and more psychologically distant from society, and the individual becomes alienated from society and himself/herself. For this reason, individuals today have entered the process of constructing themselves virtually in terms of identity construction and self-presentation in digital network environments (Aydoğan Palaz, 2023).

Due to the emergence of new forms of socialization in the digital network society, it has become possible to talk about both the real selves and digital selves of individuals. Individuals who are unable to achieve the self they desire in their real social lives have been able to create a new self and edit these selves in the way they want thanks to the newly formed digital platforms. In this way, individuals can realize the ideal self they desire in virtual environments (Okcebe, 2019).

In conclusion, with the spread of digital networks all over the world in the network society, every development in social life has made the individual's culture, interactions, behaviors, in short, the entire life of the individual has become virtual. Humans currently live in a digital universe woven with digital networks. As networked human life has gained a digital characteristic in global and local terms, time and space have also become digitized. While these

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virtual lives take place in virtual environments, identities are constructed and maintained in parallel with virtual lives in virtual environments, and a digital self-presentation is exhibited accordingly. In these virtual environments, identities that are individualized, individualized, emphasizing difference, selfish, lacking empathy, libertarian, easily influenced, fast-changing and quick-changing on a global scale are put forward and self-presentations are made. The reason why identity has these qualities and the self is presented in this way is that people lead a digital lifestyle based on technology and the internet. The lives of individuals have become a digital lifestyle connected to the internet like air, water and bread. Like the whole life of people, their feelings and thoughts are also formed and shaped according to digital networks. Hence, as social life is digitized, so are teeth; a digital lifestyle creates a digital identity, resulting in the presentation of a digital self.

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